

IDEA LEAGUE RESEARCH PROJECT
MASTER THESIS

Measures for Mitigating the Ongoing Bed Degradation in the Rhine River - A First Assessment Using Idealized Models of the Waal Branch

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June 24, 2018

Abstract

The Waal branch of the Rhine River is currently degrading by around 3 cm per year, which may have severe negative consequences for river functions like navigation, water supply and ecology. Various measures to mitigate the bed degradation are considered by the Dutch water management authority. Examples are sediment nourishments (SN), the construction of longitudinal dams (LD), and side channels (SC). However, no indicative information has been provided yet on how these measures affect the morphodynamic equilibrium state of the river and, eventually, on how effectively they would serve the goal of mitigating the bed degradation. The present work seeks to fill this knowledge gap in providing a first assessment using both idealized analytical and numerical models of the three measures named above.

We have focused on studying the effects of the measures on the equilibrium channel slope and bed surface texture of the main channel and on how the river bed adjusts to the changes over time. Aiming at comparing the orders of magnitudes of the effects, we have chosen an idealized way of modeling the measures. We have assumed decreased discharge and sediment load values in the LD and SC case, an increased sediment supply value in the SN case, and furthermore, a reduced main channel width in the case of LD. The way of schematizing the measures has been decided upon based on the findings of literature research and the consultation of various experts.

Given the limitations of the approach, the results of the models indicate that SN increase the equilibrium bed slope of an idealized Waal River most effectively. The bed adjustments may, however, take several centuries until an equilibrium state is reached. According to the results of the models, SN also lead to coarsening, whereas LD and SC, as they have been modeled here, almost have no effect on the equilibrium surface texture of the main river channel. A negative aspect of SN is the fact that they may be accompanied by initial degradation, which could negatively affect the river functions in the short term. Another disadvantage is that SN require that suitable material has to be provided continuously to nourish the river. Depending on the design, also LD and SC may serve to mitigate the bed degradation. This may, for instance, be the case if they lead to an extraction of one fourth of the water discharge from the main channel. Yet, this condition is unlikely to be fulfilled in the Waal River due to its navigation function and associated drought restrictions.

The resulting slope and surface texture values have been proven to be particularly sensitive to the assumption of the gravel supply parameter. At current, the effect of mitigation measures on this parameter is of high uncertainties and so are, hence, the results of the models.

In view of the results of the models, we conclude that a combination of different measures may be promising for solving the bed degradation problem in the Waal River and that further research should be done regarding the assumptions that underlie the models.

Preface

Coming back to Delft to finalize my environmental engineering studies has truly been a great privilege to me. However, all good things must come to an end and I would like to express my gratitude.

I want to start by thanking the IDEA League for funding this project and my former professor and boss Heribert Nacken for the straightforward organization on the part of RWTH Aachen University.

I am, furthermore, very grateful to the various experts who answered my questions patiently, provided me with helpful advice and in doing so steered the direction of the project. This has been particularly the case for Erik Mosselman, Hermjan Barneveld and Ralph Schielen, who spent valuable time and effort in guiding me as my committee.

My greatest appreciation goes to my supervisor Astrid Blom for always having been reliable and supportive and for communicating clearly and openly.

I would also like to thank Meles Siele, Liselot Arkesteijn and Víctor Chavarrías of the Department of Hydraulic Engineering at Delft University of Technology. Their support of both technical and mental nature has meant a lot and has made the time at TU Delft very pleasurable.

Last but not least, I want to thank Alicia Fernández Lezaun and my friends and family, who have been closest to me, for their encouragement of various kinds throughout my studies.

Yes, it is true that all good things must come to an end. But it is the connection to people, the skills and the memories that remain and that I will take with me on my next journey from engineering to social sciences. It is also what gives me confidence to pursue my aim of combining the two disciplines and eventually contributing to the protection of human rights, in particular regarding a safe environment.

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List of Abbreviations

AM	A shida and M ichiue
B	channel width
BC	b ase c ase
c_f	non-dimensional friction coefficient
C	Chézy roughness coefficient
DBR	D uurzame B odemligging R ijntakken
D_g	characteristic diameter of the gravel fraction
D_s	characteristic diameter of the sand fraction
DVR	D uurzame V aardiepte R ijndelta
EH	E ngelund and H ansen
F_{k0}	equilibrium surface sand content
g	acceleration due to gravity
HBL	h ydrograph b oundary l ayer
i_{b0}	equilibrium bed slope
L_a	active layer thickness
LD	longitudinal d ams
MPM	M eyer- P eter and M üller
PDF	p robability d ensity f unction
p	porosity
p_w	water discharge factor
Q_g	gravel load
Q_s	sand load
Q_w	water discharge
RQ	r esearch q uestion
RvR	R uimte voor de R ivier
SC	side c hannels
SN	sediment n ourishments
WC	W ilcock and C rowe

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Objective

Bed degradation is the dominant morphological process along the Rhine River as well as some reaches of other engineered rivers around the world such as the Danube River, the Mississippi River and the Yangtze River (Mosselman et al., 2004; Gözl, 2008; Wang et al., 2007; Blom, 2016). Degradation, in this context, refers to the lowering of the elevation of a river bed by erosion (Briaud and Hunt, 2006). Along with aggradation (the opposite process due to deposition) it determines the planform and cross-sectional shape of a river (Mugade and Sapkale, 2015). Free-flowing rivers tend to reach an erosion-deposition equilibrium (Das et al., 2014). The ongoing bed degradation is, thus, a river's response to a disturbance of this equilibrium. In the upstream part of the Dutch Rhine River, this state of disequilibrium implies an average net bed degradation of 1 to 2cm/a (Blom, 2016).

A lot of research is currently done and has already been done on the causes of the bed degradation. These causes comprise, among others, large-scale river training, extensive dredging of sediment as well as the construction of dams (Blom, 2016). The greatest anthropogenic changes in the Rhine River, contributing to the current degradation, were initiated by Johann Gottfried Tulla in the 19th century. Aiming at improving the navigability of the river, reducing the flood risk and eliminating malaria, he shortened, straightened and canalized parts of the German Rhine River (Cioc, 2009). Apart from the positive effects, this standardization, however, has also led to temporarily increased flow velocities (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). Eventually, the measures have led to a milder slope being required to transport the same amount of sediment; the river responds by degrading. In addition to that, in the 20th century dams have been built upstream of Iffezheim (Figure 1.2), which significantly trap sediment (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017; Kondolf, 1997).

Another factor that is affected by those changes is the surface texture of the river bed. If, for instance, the river's capacity of transporting sediment increases due to standardization, it could not only result in a milder slope but, due to selective erosion, also in textural coarsening (Montgomery and Buffington, 1998), which is to be investigated. The same may hold true when the sediment supply is cut off below dams (Dietrich et al., 1989). A coarser river bed is more stable as coarse grains are less mobile than fine grains (Parker et al., 1982). Besides that, the surface texture also affects the flow velocities and the bed shear stress (Montgomery and Buffington, 1998). In other words, there is a dynamic feedback between the surface texture and the morphodynamics of a river and thus the bed degradation and its consequences (Montgomery and Buffington, 1998; Dietrich et al., 1989; Lisle et al., 1993). For this reason, when studying the bed degradation, both slope and surface texture should be considered.

The resulting ongoing bed degradation in the Rhine River has potential negative consequences for river functions. These functions are, among others, navigation, water supply, structure stability and ecology (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: River functions possibly being affected by the ongoing bed degradation.

Figure 1.2: Map of the free-flowing Rhine River with locations of already implemented mitigation measures; river kilometer in brackets.

In order to avoid the potential negative consequences, measures for mitigating the ongoing bed degradation have been developed and have already partly been implemented. These include sediment nourishments, longitudinal dams, side channels, the adjustment of groynes and dikes, and the relocation of dikes (RWS, 2016a; Puhmann et al., 2009). As they seek to support a complex combination of river functions, these measures should be investigated carefully. So far, however, the knowledge base seems to be rather fragmentary. This is the background of the present project. In the scope of this project, the first three of the mitigation measures named above are studied by means of both literature research and idealized models. The broader aim is to eventually support decision-making processes regarding measures for mitigating the bed degradation. The reach that will be focused on in this research is the Waal River, which is the main branch of the Rhine River delta (Figure 1.2). It is currently degrading by around 3 cm/a (RWS, 2016b). Being one of the busiest shipping routes in the world, it plays an important role for both the Dutch and the German economy (Mosselman et al., 2004; Euwe, 2012). Hence, along with other negative effects, an ongoing bed degradation in the Waal River can have severe economic consequences for both countries.

1.2 Research Questions

In view of the broader aim of this work mentioned in the previous chapter, the main objective is to provide an indicative assessment of sediment nourishments (SN), longitudinal dams (LD), and side channels (SC) regarding the mitigation of bed degradation in the Waal branch of the Rhine River. Based on this objective, the following main research question has been formulated:

How can we provide an indicative assessment of the effectivity of SN, LD, and SC regarding the mitigation of bed degradation in the Waal River?

This question will be approached based on five subquestions (RQ):

1. How can we schematize the three measures in idealized analytical and numerical models?
2. How do the three measures affect the equilibrium state regarding channel slope and the bed surface texture?
3. What is the time scale of the adjustment of the bed elevation and bed surface texture?
4. How sensitive are the results of the analytical models to the settings of various parameters?
5. How effectively would the three measures serve the goal of mitigating the bed degradation?

1.3 Approach

In order to answer the first RQ, a literature survey has been carried out. Besides that, twelve experts have been interviewed, mainly from the Netherlands and Germany, with different backgrounds related to the topic of bed degradation. A list of the names of these experts can be found in Appendix A. The insights gained during the interviews as well as the literature survey have steered the direction of the further course of the project.

As mentioned before, free-flowing rivers tend to reach an erosion-deposition equilibrium (Das et al., 2014). This holds true when the flow statistics, sediment supply, and base level vary around stable values for a long time (Blom et al., 2017). On the basis of this equilibrium state, more specifically the equilibrium bed slope and bed surface texture, conclusions for the effectivity of the three measures are drawn. Hence, aiming at answering the second RQ, four analytical models have been compared with one another regarding these two parameters: an idealized model of the Waal River, in the following referred to as the base case (BC), and three cases where in each case one of the three measures is considered. The modeling approach used is based on Blom et al. (2017). In addition to the analytical models, we have used the one-dimensional numerical research code Elv that solves the backwater equation (Parker, 2004) to provide information on the time scale of the adjustments. The fourth RQ is answered by means of a simple sensitivity analysis of the main parameters used for the analytical results. Finally, all the information is gathered and interpreted. This is to provide an indicative assessment of how well the three measures serve the goal of mitigating the bed degradation.

Figure 1.3: Outline of the thesis.

1.4 Thesis Outline

The thesis is composed of six chapters (Figure 1.3). In Chapter 2, the state-of-the-art knowledge of the three mitigation measures is gathered. This includes an overview of measures that have already been implemented in the Rhine River and forms the basis for the models developed in Chapter 3. The model approaches that are used to answer the research questions are explained in more detail in Chapter 3 as well as their underlying assumptions. The results for the various model runs are then presented in Chapter 4. In Chapter 5, those results are then discussed. This forms the basis for the main conclusions of this project and recommendations for future research which are summarized in Chapter 6.

2 The Three Measures

This chapter describes various aspects of the three measures sediment nourishments (SN), longitudinal dams (LD) and side channels (SC), which are object of the research project. However, two remarks are to be made beforehand. First, it should be noted that, apart from those three measures, there are other ones potentially mitigating bed degradation, that are not addressed in this project. These are, for instance, fixed bed constructions or the adjustment of groynes (shortening, lengthening, lowering) (RWS, 2016a). Second, we investigate the three measures in a separate manner. According to the DVR study (Sustainable Fairway Rhine-delta) (RWS, 2016a) and the more recent DBR study (Sustainable Bed Elevation Rhine Branches), however, combining constructive (or hard) measures, such as LD and SC, and sediment management (or soft) measures, such as SN, is most promising for solving the bed degradation problem. This corresponds to the opinion of the vast majority of the experts who have been interviewed. We believe that it is nevertheless useful to investigate the effects of the measures individually. Eventually, based on those considerations, effective measure combinations can be developed in a future project.

2.1 Sediment Nourishments

Sediment nourishment (SN) (in Dutch “sediment suppleties”, in German “Geschiebezugaben”) means artificially feeding the river with sediment (Gölz, 1994). Figure 2.1 shows a barge nourishing sediment as well as a schematic of the concept of the measure. SN, thus, dynamically stabilize the river bed and, hence, have the potential to mitigate bed degradation (Gölz, 1994). Apart from immediate stabilization, they can also be a sediment source for reaches further downstream of the SN location (Gölz et al., 2006). As the migration of sediment, however, is rather slow, it can take several years to decades until the river bed of downstream reaches is affected (Gölz et al., 2006). Besides, optimal stabilization at one location does not necessarily imply the same positive effects for downstream reaches. In fact, as will be explained later on, SN can even result in increased bed degradation downstream of the SN location. Two main controlling factors for the effect of SN, apart from location and frequency, are the volume that is nourished and its grain size distribution, determining the downstream migration (Gölz et al., 2006). It is, hence, important to carefully determine whether, and if so, how much sediment of a certain composition should be nourished at a particular location.

In Germany, SN have become an accepted method in river engineering and are being applied more and more on German Federal waterways (Gölz, 2008). **When the furthest downstream weir of the Rhine River was put into operation at Iffezheim in 1978 (Figure 1.2), SN were, for the first time, initiated to avoid bed degradation (Gölz, 2008).** Ever since, around **480 000 t/a of a sand-gravel-mixture** (density around 2650 kg/m^3) have been nourished at that location (km 336 to 338) and **in smaller quantities in the Mittelrhein (km 534 to 582)** (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017; Boettcher, 2013). The nourishments have been adjusted locally over time and serve to stabilize the river bed (Gölz, 2008). Besides

Figure 2.1: Sediment Nourishments (SN), here a barge nourishing near Iffezheim (top) and a schematic of the concept (bottom) (after Boettcher, 2013).

that, however, accounting for about half of the sediment load at that location (Frings et al., 2014; Weichert et al., 2010), the SN at Iffezheim are also an essential control for the sediment management of the whole Rhine River (Gölz et al., 2006) as they influence the bed elevation of river reaches downstream (Gölz et al., 2006).

In the Niederrhein, sediment has been nourished at nine different locations, successfully counteracting the bed degradation (WSV, 2008). Here, as referred to and further explained in Chapter 3.3, they make up a twelfold increase of the gravel supply from upstream and an increase of 30 % of the sand load (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). All together, in the course of the SN in the Ober-, Mittel- and Niederrhein, around 500 000 t of gravel-sized material is fed annually along the 500 km free flowing Rhine in Germany (Gölz, 2008).

As mentioned before, upstream bed level changes transfer to downstream reaches (Sieben, 2009). Morphodynamic changes in the Niederrhein, hence, affect the Dutch Rhine branches (Sieben, 2009). This means that, if on a longer time scale migrating downstream, the SN in the Niederrhein may contribute to the stabilization of the Dutch Rhine branches (Sieben, 2009). On the other hand, however, according to Blom (2016) and as pointed out later on, they might also first lead to downstream degradation. This is because the relatively coarse sediment that is nourished is comparably less mobile (Blom, 2016). Hence, compared to downstream, the sediment transport capacity in the nourishment area is smaller, leading to downstream degradation. In other words, the SN of the Niederrhein may already contribute to the current bed degradation in the Waal River and the Pannerdensch Kanaal (Figure 1.2) (Blom, 2016).

In the Netherlands, to assess the applicability of SN in Dutch river management, a pilot study has been issued by the executive agency Rijkswaterstaat of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management (Niesten and Becker, 2018; Niesten et al., 2017). In the framework of the pilot project, a first nourishment was carried out in 2016 close to Lobith (Figure 1.2) (Niesten and Becker, 2018; Niesten et al., 2017). Here, a total amount of approximately 190 000 t of a gravel-granite mixture has been nourished (Emmanouil, 2017). In Chapter 3.3, this quantity is discussed in more detail. A second nourishment at the same location is scheduled for 2019 (Niesten and Becker, 2018). To assess the effectivity of the first nourishment, the hydraulic and morphodynamic response is currently studied using field observations and numerical models. As mentioned above, granite, which can be followed by radiometric observations (Medusa method) (Snellen et al., 2013), was part of the nourishment material. Hence, for monitoring purposes, monthly Medusa-maps

have been made. Apart from that, bed level-maps have been created, water levels and discharges have been recorded continuously at Lobith, and grain size distributions and flow velocities have been measured at specific locations. According to Niesten and Becker (2018), from the observations it can be seen, so far, that the nourishment effectively increases the upstream water level. However, no conclusion regarding the contribution to mitigating bed degradation can yet be drawn (Niesten and Becker, 2018). Due to the rather long time scale of morphodynamic change, time and further research will provide reliable results regarding the effectivity of the SN in the Bovenrijn.

In summary, we can conclude from the literature survey that SN have already been proven a successful measure for mitigating the bed degradation at several locations in the German Rhine River. One of the disadvantages, however, is that suitable material has to be provided and nourished to the river continuously (Gölz, 1994). It is for this reason that it might be expedient to investigate in how far SN can be reduced by combining them with other hard measures, such as LD and SC.

2.2 Longitudinal Dams

Longitudinal dams (LD) (in Dutch “langsdammen”, in German “Parallelwerke/ Leitwerke”) are river training structures which are aligned parallel to the river bank. They divide the channel into a main channel and a secondary channel (Figure 2.2) (RWS, 2016a). The underlying idea of LD is to change the distribution of water and sediment or more precisely to reduce the flow velocities and to increase the proportionate sediment load in the main channel (Eerden, 2013; Collas et al., 2018). In doing so, they too have the potential of mitigating bed degradation.

In the Netherlands, three LD have been built in 2016 within the scope of a pilot project called WaalSamen, initiated by Rijkswaterstaat (Collas et al., 2016). Here, over a reach of about ten kilometers in the Waal River (km 911 to 921), they have replaced the former groynes in the inner bend (Collas et al., 2016) (Figure 2.2). By doing so, they have, hence, reduced the width of the main channel by about 30 m. The crest height of the three LD exceeded by the water level at discharges higher than 2606 m³/s at Lobith (RWS, 2011).

By dividing the river channel into two channels, they aim at serving multiple functions (Eerden, 2013; Collas et al., 2018):

Figure 2.2: Longitudinal dams (LD), here type WaalSamen: top view (left), schematic of the cross section (right) (after RWS, 2012 and RU, 2017).

1. to increase and maintain water depth for navigation,
2. to increase discharge capacity and thus improve flood safety,
3. to facilitate the safe discharge of ice to protect hydraulic infrastructure and river dikes,
4. to reduce fairway maintenance costs (dredging), and
5. to increase habitat diversity and stability by creating sheltered secondary channels.

In view of the above, the construction of LD have been one of the advices given by the DVR study to mitigate bed degradation (RWS, 2016b).

Even though the design of LD has been extensively studied by means of numerical models (e.g. Huthoff, 2011) and in laboratory experiments (Vermeulen et al., 2014), the morphodynamic response is yet unclear (Jammers et al., 2017; Van Weerdenburg, 2018). It strongly depends on the dimensions (length and height) of the inlets and openings (Jammers et al., 2017). These are sill-type structures that can be changed relatively easily (Jammers et al., 2017). Understanding the bed load processes over the sills is the key challenge to make long-term morphological predictions (Jammers et al., 2017).

Another determining factor for the morphodynamic response is the location of the upstream head of an LD (T.B. Le et al., 2018; Le et al., 2018). According to T.B. Le et al. (2018), a system of two parallel channels divided by an LD has the tendency of becoming unstable (e.g. one of the channels silts up). In order to slow down unwanted silting up, the upstream head should optimally be located at the top of a bar (Le et al., 2018; Smith, 2015). When complying with this condition, the morphological changes develop rather slowly which makes them manageable (Le et al., 2018). Furthermore, based on experiments in a physical scale model, it was found that the local morphological response close to the upstream head of an LD are limited (Vermeulen et al., 2014). According to Vermeulen et al. (2014), depositional areas which could possibly cause shoals for navigation are not to be expected at this location. The field data analysis of Van Weerdenburg (2018), on the contrary, does indicate a sedimentation front at the upstream head of the LD which might widen and propagate in downstream direction.

Van Weerdenburg (2018), furthermore, observes an erosion pit of a current depth of 1 m and a length of 2 km just downstream of the LD. This corresponds to Coumou (2018) that downstream of LD more erosion is expected, e.g. due to sediment being trapped by the LD. In any case, it should be noted that LD can only reduce bed degradation in the river sections with LD (Coumou, 2018). For this reason, Coumou (2018) as well as some of the experts who have been interviewed suggest a combination of LD with SN to stabilize the bed in the entire Waal River.

In the river reach where LD were built, the bed elevation and the sediment composition of the surface texture have and will further be determined by, respectively, multi-beam echo sounding measurements and samples from the bed surface taken by a hamon grab (Van Weerdenburg, 2018). This has been part of the monitoring program of Rijkswaterstaat (Van Weerdenburg, 2018). We expect that in the coming years the data will provide further information on the effectivity of LD regarding the goal of mitigating bed degradation.

In Germany, LD were placed at several locations in the Rhine River already at the end of the 20th century. They were mainly implemented with the purpose of protecting river banks and improving the ecology and not regarding the mitigation of the ongoing bed degradation (RWS, 2016a). According to the interview outcomes, however, also the Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau (BAW) and the Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde (BfG), which

are the two most relevant authorities for inland rivers in Germany (Mosselman et al., 2004), show interest in LD as a future measures for mitigating bed degradation in the Rhine River.

2.3 Side Channels

Also side channels (SC or secondary channels) (in Dutch “nevengeulen”, in German “Seitengerinne/ Nebengerinne”) have received increasing attention as a measure to counteract bed degradation (Klop, 2009). They are defined as channels in the floodplain which convey water (Mosselman, 2001). Their main purpose is to increase the river conveyance capacity and reduce the flood level (Barneveld and Wegman, 2018). Apart from that, SC also give room for ecological enhancement, due to shallow water and shelter from the navigation-induced physical loads (Simons et al., 2001). If implemented on a longer reach, e.g. in the form of a braiding chain of SC, they may, however, also be effective regarding the mitigation of bed degradation (Barneveld and Wegman, 2018). This is due to the fact that diverting flow towards a side channel can reduce the transport capacity of the main channel, and hence, lead to an increased equilibrium slope and therefore to sedimentation in the main channel (Barneveld and Wegman, 2018; Simons et al., 2001). In general, SC are unstable and if aggrading, they are expected to be closed within 5 to 15 years (Mosselman, 2001). For this reason, periodic excavations are needed to maintain them (Mosselman, 2001; Kleinhans et al., 2013).

In order to keep aggradation at low rates, Mosselman (2001) suggests the following conditions as a first guideline:

- The ratio between the side channel length and the main channel length between the offtake and the confluence should be smaller than 1.5. Van Denderen et al. (2017) found that if the SC is much shorter than the main channel, the SC may become the dominant channel.
- The angle between the SC and the main channel at the offtake should be smaller than 90° .
- The average angle between the side channel and the floodplain flow lines during a flood should be smaller than 45° .
- SC should preferably take off from an outer bend of the main channel.

Furthermore, Van Denderen et al. (2017) found that bend flow (e.g. spiral flow that is directed towards the inner bend near the bed) may increase the sediment load to one of the channels and that the transverse bed slope upstream from the bifurcation point can stabilize a side channel system.

Until the river normalizations of the late 19th and early 20th century, SC were a common phenomenon in the floodplain of the Rhine River (Schropp and Jans, 2000). Naturally, however, SC only occur if a river is relatively wide (relation of width to depth of at least 100), which makes their natural occurrence in the Rhine River impossible nowadays (Wolters et al., 2001). Yet SC do exist in the German and Dutch Rhine River, having been constructed by man over the past centuries, mainly with the aim to improve flood risk and ecology (Schropp and Jans, 2000).

The possibilities for man-made SC in the floodplain of Dutch rivers have been studied since 1989 (Simons et al., 2001). Being sufficiently dynamic in comparison to the other Dutch

Figure 2.3: Side channels (SC), here Flutmulde Rees: top view (left), inlet sill for controlling the water level (right), schematic of the cross section (bottom) (after WSV, 2016).

Rhine branches, the Bovenrijn and the Waal River are most suitable for the construction of SC (Wolters et al., 2001). However, due to the great proportion of sand load in the Waal River, here, the risk of closure as a result of sedimentation is relatively high (Wolters et al., 2001). Besides that, due to its navigation function and associated drought restrictions, the discharge available to the SC is limited to only a few percent of the total river discharge (Schropp and Jans, 2000). Yet, SC that extract a larger amount of the water discharge have a greater effect on the morphodynamics (Schuurman, 2012). For those reasons, it is hard to build SC in the Waal River that are morphologically active and, at the same time, are not blocked quickly (Simons et al., 2001).

The SC Opijnen, Beneden Leeuwen and van der Gamerensche Waard were the first SC to be constructed as pilot projects in the Waal River between 1994 and 1999 (Klop, 2009; Simons et al., 2001). Their discharge capacities are respectively a maximum of 1.2%, 0.5% and 3% (Schropp and Jans, 2000; Simons et al., 2001). From the monitoring programs, it was concluded that they aggrade on average 8 cm/a (Klop, 2009). No information, however, could be found on the impact of the SC on bed level in the main channel.

In the context of the ongoing bed degradation in the Rhine River, the so-called Flutmulde Rees in the German Niederrhein is an example of a side channel explicitly designed with the objective to mitigate the bed degradation in the main channel (WSV, 2016) (Figure 1.2 and 2.3). The channel was officially opened in 2015 by the Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsamt (WSA) Duisburg-Rhein, which is one of the regional agencies responsible for the administration of the German Rhine River (WSV, 2016). The Flutmulde Rees can take up to 18% of the discharge of the main channel (WSV, 2017). The inlet sill at the upstream end of the channel (Figure 2.3) has two purposes. The first purpose is to avoid that the water level of the Rhine River falls below the mean water level. Due to the inlet sill, water only enters the side channel if the water level in the main channel exceeds the mean water level by more than 0.8 m. Second, it is supposed to serve as a control to avoid sedimentation and erosion in the side channel.

The monitoring of the Flutmulde Rees includes the regular observation of changes of biotic and abiotic factors (WSV, 2016). Annually, the state is then assessed based on the degree of achievement of sub-goals (WSV, 2016). According to the most recent assessment, most of the defined goals, such as the prevention of negative effects on the water level in the main

channel, are completely or at least partly achieved (WSV, 2016). However, as it is too early to draw final conclusion about the morphodynamic response, the goal “stabilization of the river bed” cannot be assessed yet (WSV, 2016).

We expect that in the future the results of the monitoring of the Flutmulde Rees and comparable SC in combination with numerical models will lead to a better understanding of the relevant morphological processes. Various experts highlighted, for instance, the effect of ships on the development of both main and side channel ,which is insufficiently studied so far. A better understanding of such factors may eventually help to improve design guidelines for man-made side channels aiming at mitigating bed degradation.

3 Description of the Models

Models are, by definition, simplified representations of the real world (Wagener, 2003). The simplification takes place in space and time and has significant consequences for the model results (Wagener, 2003). For this reason, it is very important to carefully determine the model type that is appropriate to achieve a certain objective, as well as the input parameters. Hence, the modeling process begins with a clear statement of the objectives of the model (Tedeschi, 2006).

The objective of the model in this work is particularly aligned with RQ 2, 3 and 4 as formulated in Chapter 1.2. The model should provide information on the equilibrium slope and surface texture of an idealized Waal River. Furthermore, it should serve to determine the development from one equilibrium state to another, hence the time scale of the adjustments. This is to eventually draw conclusions on the effectivity of the measures regarding the mitigation of the bed degradation in the Waal River (RQ 5). The subsequent modeling steps are described and performed as follows. The first part of this chapter is devoted to the model selection. Its accompanying assumptions are described in the second part. In the third part, the general schematization of the Waal River, which forms the basis for the case considerations, is explained along with the assumptions that have been made to model the three measures.

3.1 Selection of the Models

Two different modeling approaches have been selected to answer the RQs: one analytical approach based on Blom et al. (2017), and one one-dimensional numerical approach based on the time-marching research code Elv that has been developed at the Water Lab of Delft University of Technology. The goal of this work is to provide a first rough assessment of the effects of the three measures on the bed slope and surface texture. For this reason, it has been decided that regarding the numerical approach one-dimensional models, thus width-averaged values, give sufficient information (De Vries, 1993).

The analytical approach presented in Blom et al. (2017) provides the relations describing the equilibrium bed slope and bed surface texture (RQ 2). The analysis extends the unisize sediment analysis described in De Vries (1974) to mixed-size sediment conditions (Blom et al., 2017). Furthermore, it is an extension of the approach of Blom et al. (2016) to a variable flow rate (Blom et al., 2017) (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1: Analytical relations for the equilibrium state of an alluvial river.

	Constant flow	Variable flow
Unisize sediment		De Vries (1974)
Mixed-size sediment	Blom et al (2016)	Blom et al (2017)

An extensive list of all underlying assumptions can be found in Blom et al. (2017). The main assumptions that underlie both the analytical and the numerical model are listed below:

1. The analytical model results only hold true in the river's normal flow zone.
2. As initial condition in the numerical model, we assume the equilibrium state of the base case (BC).
3. We assume a temporally constant channel width B .
4. The river cross section is assumed to be rectangular. There is no distinction between flow through the main channel and the floodplains.
5. The flow is steady for each value of the flow rate, also termed an alternating steady discharge. In other words, it is assumed that flood waves are infinitely long and propagate infinitely fast.
6. We apply the sediment transport relation by Wilcock and Crowe (2003).
7. The analysis is limited to two sediment fractions (gravel and sand).

These assumptions are explained and discussed in the following chapter.

3.2 Underlying Assumptions

1. The analytical model results only hold true in the river's normal flow zone.

When studying a fluvial reach of variable flow under a constant base level (e.g. sea water level) three zones can be distinguished: the hydrograph boundary layer (HBL), the normal flow zone, and the backwater zone (Figure 3.1) (Blom et al., 2017). The HBL results from possible differences between the distribution of the sediment supply and the distribution of the sediment transport capacity. It is in the HBL that the distribution adjusts to the normal flow zone distribution (Blom et al., 2017). This adjustment causes fluctuations in bed elevation, slope and surface texture (Blom et al., 2017). In the normal flow zone, on the contrary, the river geometry is determined by the long-term mean value of the sediment supply and not by its short-term temporal variations (Blom et al., 2017).

The normal flow zone extends downstream up to the location where the flow is affected by backwater due to the downstream boundary. Here, the water surface is controlled by the water surface base level (Blom et al., 2017). As mentioned earlier, to extend the findings from the analytical model, also a numerical model is applied. This model, using the backwater equation and, hence, not being limited to the normal flow zone, additionally gives information about the reaches outside this zone, thus the HBL and the backwater segment. However, these values fall outside the scope of this work. The specific settings of the numerical model are listed in Table 3.2.

2. As initial condition in the numerical model, we assume the equilibrium state of the base case (BC).

We chose the equilibrium state of the BC as initial condition in considering the effects of the three measures. This approach is chosen in order to be able to assess the effects of the three measures in an isolated manner. How the effects change when overlapping with current morphodynamic changes, such as the ongoing bed degradation (Chapter 1.1), is still to be investigated.

Figure 3.1: Schematic of variable flow under a constant base level: the hydrograph boundary layer (HBL), the normal flow zone, and the backwater zone (Blom et al., 2017).

Table 3.2: Specific settings of the numerical models (*Chapter 3.3 Table 3.4).

Time step	1 d
Domain length	300 km
Streamwise discretization	1000 m
Interface type	Hirano
Active layer thickness L_a	1 m
Initial grain size distribution of the substrate	Equivalent to the one in L_a
Hydrodynamic boundary condition	Sea level 0 m
Morphodynamic boundary condition	Case specific values*
Initial condition	Base case (BC) equilibrium*

3. We assume a temporally constant channel width B .

In reality, a river can respond to changes by adjusting its slope, surface texture, and channel width (Blom et al., 2017). Hence, by assuming a temporally constant width of the cross section adjustments are restricted to the slope and the surface texture. This is considered reasonable for the Waal River as it is an engineered river.

4. The river cross section is assumed to be rectangular. There is no distinction between flow through the main channel and the floodplains.

This assumption is regarded an important simplification that needs to be considered when using the model results. It is a crucial factor as it implies the neglect of the floodplains (Figure 3.2). Naturally, the floodplains do convey water when the discharge exceeds the value for bankfull discharge. Here we take on a pragmatic approach: the measured values of the hydrograph are modified in such a way that values exceeding the bankfull discharge are reduced to that value. This means we are assuming that the shear stress does not further increase once the bankfull discharge is exceeded. In a subsequent research project, this simplification could be relaxed, for instance by using the one-dimensional hydraulic modeling system SOBEK-River/Estuary, which unlike Elv, accounts for non-rectangular cross sections.

5. The flow is steady for each value of the flow rate, also termed an alternating steady discharge. In other words, it is assumed that flood waves are infinitely long and propagate infinitely fast.

There are two justifications for this assumption. First, as the time scale of change in bed slope is much larger compared to the change of water discharge, the bed does not have

Figure 3.2: Schematic of the river cross section (red line indicating the water level that corresponds to a bankfull discharge).

sufficient time to adjust to the short-term discharge changes (Blom et al., 2017).

The second reason is that in this work we are considering a part of the lower course of the Rhine River. Flood waves have, hence, already diffused considerably when reaching the area under consideration (Blom et al., 2017). The assumption that flood waves are infinitely long and propagate infinitely fast therefore seems acceptable.

6. We apply the sediment transport relation by Wilcock and Crowe (2003).

When predicting morphodynamic behavior, a sediment transport relation is needed (Janssen, 2013). Here, the sediment transport relation by Wilcock and Crowe (2003) (WC) is used for both models. However, there are several other empirical relations which have all been derived under different conditions. It is important to be aware of those conditions and to critically consider the applicability to the individual case, here the idealized Waal River. To give an indication for the sensitivity of the results with regard to the selected transport relation, three other relations are tested in the analytical model. The main distinguishing criteria of those relations are presented in Table 3.3 together with the respective characteristics.

Sediment grains will start to move if the resisting force is overcome. A threshold-based load relation implies the assumption that the gravel is immobile for small flow values (Blom et al., 2017). In other words, in the case of Meyer-Peter and Müller (1948) (MPM) and Ashida and Michiue (1972) (AM) gravel is transported only if the flow exceeds a threshold value. For the two non-threshold based relations, Wilcock and Crowe (2003) (WC) and Engelund and Hansen (1967) (EH), any flow value contributes to transporting the sediment downstream. Assuming zero transport for flow values below the threshold, threshold-based relations may underpredict the sediment mobility (Blom et al., 2017). Non-threshold-based relations may, on the contrary, overpredict it.

Another distinguishing criterion is the consideration of hiding and exposure. In the case of mixed-size sediment, such as the gravel-sand bed of the Waal River, grains can influence each other (Parker et al., 1982). Larger grains are more exposed to the flow than smaller grains, which can hide behind them. Hence, larger grains are relatively more mobile in a mixture than in uni-size sediment of that size (Parker et al., 1982). In this work, all transport relations, except for EH, include the effect of hiding and exposure.

We also need to stress the experimental grain size range under which the formulas have been derived. The WC relation is based on flume experiments on transport of sand-gravel mixtures (Van Der Scheer et al., 2002), thus under grain size conditions comparable to the ones in the Waal River. The experimental grain size range does not necessarily determine whether a relation gives proper results in a certain case or not. However, it is a factor that should be taken into account when drawing conclusions from a model's results. Finally,

Table 3.3: Sediment transport relations (WC = Wilcock and Crowe; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen; *derived without hiding and exposure but can, however, be combined with the Egiazaroff (1965) (here) or the Ashida and Michiue (1972) hiding and exposure factor; **with or without hiding and exposure (here with)) (Van Der Scheer et al., 2002).

	Threshold-based	Hiding and exposure	Grain sizes
WC	No	Yes	4.53 - 10.22 mm
MPM	Yes	Yes*	0.4 - 29 mm
AM	Yes	Yes**	~ 1.7 mm
EH	No	No	0.19 –0.93mm

Figure 3.3: Modes of sediment transport.

it should be noted that all relations are used with the original settings, hence without calibration.

7. The analysis is limited to two sediment fractions (gravel and sand).

In general, sediment can be transported in two ways: by rolling, sliding and saltation on the river bed, as so-called bed load (sand and fine gravel), or in suspension in the fluid (for some time) as suspended load (clay, silt, fine sands). Per definition, the bed load and the part of the suspended load that interacts with the river bed are together defined as the bed material load (Figure 3.3) (Travaglio, 1981). This is in contrast to wash load which permanently is in suspension and does not exchange with the bed sediment. When studying the river bed regarding slope and surface texture, it is hence important to take all bed material load fractions into account.

The most recent study of the sediment budget of the Rhine River is Hillebrand and Frings (2017). This work comprises the results of numerous morphodynamic studies carried out during the period 1991 to 2010 (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). For the Waal River (km 868 to 951), a sediment balance is provided for each of the following fractions: smaller than 0.063 mm (silt, clay), 0.063 mm to 2 mm (sand), 2 mm to 16 mm (fine gravel), and 16 mm to 63 mm (gravel) (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). As we limit our analysis to bed material load, the latter three fractions are taken into account in the models. However, given the high uncertainty of the values given in the study (e.g. $\pm 100\%$ for the gravel fraction) and the high degree of simplification of the assessment, not distinguishing between all the three seems acceptable in the scope of this work. For this reason, both gravel fractions are considered collectively as one fraction. The gravel load value, given in Table 3.4 for the base case (BC), is therefore the total incoming load of fine gravel and gravel.

Figure 3.4: Schematic of the considered cases (dashed lines indicating the areas that are investigated; colored arrows or lines indicating that the input parameters differ from the BC values).

3.3 Considered Cases

Having selected the model types, it is now time to define the four cases: the base case (BC) without any measures and three additional cases, one for each of the measures (SN; LD; SC). Before the main input parameters are discussed, the general schematization concept is explained.

Here, in view of the goal to provide an order of magnitude comparison, it has been decided to limit the modification of the input values to four of the eight parameters in total as given in Table 3.4. These are channel width (B), incoming gravel load (Q_g), incoming sand load (Q_s), and incoming water discharge (Q_w). An overview of which of these parameter values is altered in which case (SN, LD, SC) is provided in Figure 3.4 and Table 3.4.

The approach has been discussed and decided upon in consultation with various experts interviewed beforehand. SN are often schematized in a different way in 1D models, by elevating the bed level at the location where sediment is nourished. This hump is then diffusing and after a certain period of time the original bed level is restored, unless this process is repeated regularly. As the focus of this project is on changes of the equilibrium state, a more straightforward approach is chosen, namely to increase the incoming sediment load instead. This approach is also presented by Viparelli et al. (2011) for modeling gravel nourishments in gravel bed rivers. Here, it is based on Parker et al. (2007). We assume a permanent increase or, in the case of LD and SC, decrease of the incoming sediment load.

Another important remark related to the schematization is that, as pointed out in Figure 3.4, we only consider the main channel, indicated with dashed lines. Thus, for the LD and SC case our analysis will provide no information about morphodynamic change in the secondary or side channels.

Table 3.4: Input values for the considered cases (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels; B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

	Unit	BC	SN	LD	SC	Range
B	m	260	260	230	260	± 20 m
D_g	mm	10	10	10	10	2–16 mm
D_s	mm	1	1	1	1	0.063–1.5 mm
Q_g	m^3/s	0.81×10^{-3}	1.63×10^{-3}	0.81×10^{-3}	0.81×10^{-3}	± 100 %
Q_s	m^3/s	6.67×10^{-3}	6.67×10^{-3}	6.33×10^{-3}	6.53×10^{-3}	± 50 %
p_w	–	1.00	1.00	0.85	0.95	± 20 %
c_f	–	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003–0.005
p	–	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.25–0.4

Figure 3.5: Top view schematic of the conditions of the numerical models.

For the numerical models, the approach is furthermore based on the assumption that the measures are implemented along the whole reach. In other words, we assume a chain of LD or SC as schematized in Figure 3.5. In Hillebrand and Frings (2017), a reach of 83 km is defined as the Waal River (km 868 to 951) (Figure 1.2). For simplicity a length of 300 km is selected to achieve a reach of around 100 km unaffected by backwater (Figure 3.1, Table 3.2).

Regarding the effect on the equilibrium slope, it should be noted that the selection of the four parameters implies a combination of counteracting effects for the LD and the SC case: Extracting water leads to a steeper slope, whereas both reducing the channel width and extracting sediment result in a milder slope (Ribberink and Sande, 1985; De Vriend, 2015). This is illustrated in Figure 3.6. A more comprehensive illustration that includes the initial flow velocities and the morphodynamic trends caused by the changes can be found in Appendix B.

In the following, the selected values for the main input parameters will be discussed.

Figure 3.6: Effects of different measures on the equilibrium slope (initial bed and water levels in the top row, bed and water levels at the new equilibrium in the bottom row) (after Crosato, 2007).

Figure 3.7: Schematic of the channel cross sections indicating the channel width for the different cases (after RWS, 2012).

They are presented in Table 3.4. In the right-hand column, a min-max range is given. This is the range that is used for the sensitivity analysis, discussed in Chapter 4.3. In this analysis, each of the given parameters is tested separately whereby respectively all the other parameters are in accordance with the original setting given in the table. However, apart from the sensitivity analysis that provides information about how equilibrium slope and surface texture change if the input values change, also the case definitions were varied. The results for extremer cases, with an increase of ten times of the gravel supply instead of a doubling for the SN case for example, can be found in the tables in Appendix C.

Parameter B

The first parameter listed in Table 3.4 is the channel width B over which sediment is transported. For the BC, the SN, and the SC case, we hence refer to the distance between the groynes on both sides of the Waal River. As mentioned before, we are only studying the main channel. For the LD case, the channel width is therefore the distance between the LD on one side and the groynes on the other side. According to RWS (2012) and verified by means of the web mapping service Google Maps, the values are around 260 m and 230 m. A schematic for the two different cross sections is provided in Figure 3.7.

Parameters D_g , D_s , Q_g , and Q_s

Those parameters all refer to the sediment supply. As mentioned in Chapter 3.2 when discussing the seventh assumption, Hillebrand and Frings (2017) is the most recent study of the sediment budget of the Rhine River. It provides value ranges for those four parameters for the Waal River, which is used as a reference for the BC. In this work, we have chosen

a sand size of 1 mm and a gravel size of 10 mm. In the sensitivity analysis, however, we do consider ranges based on the original grain size ranges given in the study. The sand and gravel load values are provided in the unit Mt/a (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). To convert those mass flow values into the required volume flow unit m^3/s , a sediment density of $2650 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ is assumed. It should be noted that gravel only makes up a small portion of the total incoming sediment load: around 10 % is gravel load, 90 % is sand load. According to Hillebrand and Frings (2017), the sand load is subject to an uncertainty of $\pm 50\%$, and the gravel fraction between 80 and 140 %. Based on this information, the min-max ranges of $\pm 50\%$ or $\pm 100\%$ have been selected for the sensitivity analysis.

The alteration of the load values for the SN, the LD, and the SC cases has been decided upon as follows. For the SN, two data sets from different locations of the Rhine River have been checked to determine a realistic load value for the Waal River. First, we compared the volumes nourished at the Niederrhein (km 646 to the Dutch-German border) and in the Bovenrijn pilot project (Chapter 2.1) to the incoming sediment load given for those reaches in Hillebrand and Frings (2017). According to Hillebrand and Frings (2017), at the Niederrhein $0.7 \text{ Mt}/\text{a}$ gravel and $0.116 \text{ Mt}/\text{a}$ sand have been nourished on average in the period between 1991 and 2010. Those values are characterized by an uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$. Compared to the sediment load values from upstream, these nourishments make up a twelvefold increase of the gravel load from upstream and an increase of 30 % of the sand load. The second location is the Bovenrijn. In the course of the pilot project, a volume of in total $70\,550 \text{ m}^3$ gravel has been nourished, with a mean grain size of around 1 cm and a sediment density of around $2650 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$ (Emmanouil, 2017). Assuming that this volume is nourished every year, evenly distributed over the year, it is equivalent to approximately a threefold increase of the incoming gravel load (Hillebrand and Frings, 2017). However, it should be noted that the values for the incoming sediment load are again of high uncertainty, and likewise are hence the factors. Here, we have decided to study the effects on the slope and the surface texture of the Waal River for a twofold increase of the incoming gravel load (Table 3.4). This corresponds to a nourishment of around $68\,000 \text{ t}/\text{a}$, again assuming a sediment density of $2650 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$. This amount is of the same order of magnitude as the volumes that have been nourished annually in the Niederrhein over the past decades (WSV, 2008).

Regarding the LD and the SC case, we assume a reduction of the incoming sand load for the LD case to a value of $6.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, meaning 5 % of extraction, and for the SC case 2 % ($6.53 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). The reduction factors have been chosen in consultation with the interviewed experts. However, as mentioned before, additional cases are considered for all the three measures in the tables in Appendix C.

Parameter p_w

The next parameter to be discussed is the water discharge. In this work, we focus on a statistical steady state and model the changing water discharge given by a hydrograph in terms of temporarily constant statistics, expressed by the probability density function (PDF) of water discharge (Blom et al., 2017). As the data series of the discharge near Lobith (Figure 1.2) is the longest (from 1901 on) compared to locations in the Waal River, we have based our study on the Lobith data series. The hydrograph for the Waal River, and hence for the BC of this study, has been derived by constantly reducing the discharge values by one-third. This is due to the fact that the Waal River transports about two-thirds of the discharge near Lobith (e.g. Hillebrand and Frings, 2017; Cioc, 2009). As mentioned when explaining the fourth assumption in the previous chapter, the hydrograph is further modified to take the neglect of the floodplains into account, which is induced by the rectangular cross section: the discharge values exceeding the bankfull discharge value

Figure 3.8: Modified hydrograph (horizontal line indicating the assumed value for bankfull discharge) (data courtesy: Rijkswaterstaat).

Figure 3.9: Modified hydrograph used as input for the base case (BC).

are reduced to the bankfull discharge value. Near Lobith, this value is around $4000 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Brandsma, 2016). Reducing it by one-third ($2667 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ in Figure 3.8) and implementing the modification, results in the hydrograph for the BC presented in Figure 3.9.

In Table 3.4, a water discharge factor is given for each of the considered cases. This is to allow for the extraction of water in the LD and the SC case. In those cases, the BC hydrograph has been multiplied by the factor 0.85, meaning a reduction of 15% of the water discharge due to the LD, and by 0.95 (reduction of 5%) in the case of SC. Those factors again are rough estimates that have been decided upon in consultation with the experts. They are relaxed by both the sensitivity analysis and the consideration of additional cases (Appendix C). A final note is made regarding the LD case. As mentioned in Chapter 2.2, the crest height of the LD is exceeded at discharges higher than $2606 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ at Lobith (around $1740 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ at the Waal River) (RWS, 2011), which is lower than the highest discharge values of the hydrograph ($0.85 \times 2667 \text{ m}^3/\text{s} = 2267 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). Furthermore, in the sensitivity analysis, values up to $2720 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ occur, which is considerably larger than the crest height value. However, we assume that there are no changes of the dynamics due to overflow of the LD.

Parameter c_f

The next section is dedicated to the non-dimensional friction coefficient c_f , which affects the total bed shear stress. This parameter is fundamental when linking flow conditions to sediment transport (Biron et al., 2004). In general, the total bed shear stress can at least be divided into two components: shear stress from skin friction due to individual grains on the river bed and shear stress from form drag due to dunes and ripples (Julien et al., 2002). There are different ways of writing the friction coefficient (Julien et al., 2002). Here, we use the non-dimensional friction coefficient c_f which varies inversely with the often used Chézy coefficient C according to the following relation:

$$c_f = g/C^2$$

At the Waal River, Chézy values of about $44 \text{ m}^{1/2}/\text{s}$ ($c_f = 0.005$) during peak discharges and else up to $55 \text{ m}^{1/2}/\text{s}$ ($c_f = 0.003$) have been measured (Julien et al., 2002). Those values are used for the sensitivity analysis. In consultation with the experts, a value of 0.004 has been selected for the general cases (Table 3.4).

Parameter p

The porosity p , which is the last parameter discussed here, indicates the void spaces of the bed material as a volume fraction over the total volume. This parameter is not part of the analytical equations and only plays a role for the numerical models. As the sensitivity analysis is limited to the analytical models a min-max range for this parameter is only listed in Table 3.4 for the sake of completeness. As can be seen in resulting figures (e.g. Figure 4.20, Appendix F), the porosity value does not influence the equilibrium slope and surface texture. According to Frings et al. (2008), the bed porosity in the Rhine River varies spatially between 0.15 and 0.35, which is less than the often-used standard value of 0.4. Here, for practical reasons, we have decided for a constant value of 0.3.

4 Results of the Models

The previous chapter was dedicated to the description of the modeling assumptions and the considered cases. This chapter presents the model results. This comprises two steps. In the first step (Chapter 4.1), we compare the equilibrium slope and surface texture predicted using the analytical models. We assess the effect of the sediment transport relation underlying the model, by comparing the slope and surface texture values predicted based on four different relations. Thereupon, we analyze the results from the numerical models, thus the adjustment of the slope and surface texture over time. Then, in the second step (Chapter 4.3), we interpret the results of the sensitivity analysis of the analytical models regarding the selected input parameters.

4.1 The Predicted Equilibrium States

The results for the equilibrium slope and bed surface sand content for the four considered cases are presented in Figure 4.1. Before comparing the values and, thus the order of magnitude of the effect of the measures (SN, LD, SC), we want to examine the predicted values for the BC. According to De Vries (1993), Sieben (2009), Sloff et al. (2014), and Blom (2016), the channel slope of the Waal River is between 1.0×10^{-4} and 1.2×10^{-4} . The equilibrium slope value predicted for the BC is, depending on the transport relation, between 0.7×10^{-4} and 1.0×10^{-4} which matches the prediction made by RWS (2016b). As it is smaller than the measured value range, it may be an explanation of the ongoing bed degradation in the Waal River, as an adjustment process towards a smaller equilibrium slope. For the surface texture, no such conclusion regarding coarsening or fining can be drawn, given the large range of the measured values: Frings et al. (2011) and Ten Brinke (2005) state a range of 50 % to 80 % of sand in the bed surface depending on the location in the Waal River; the value predicted by the models is around 50 and 60 %, depending on the transport relation.

Assuming the current slope range given above and a river length of 83 km, the slope adjustment towards the equilibrium corresponds to an approximate total degradation upstream of the river of between 0.5 and 4.5 m. According to RWS (2016a), the bed of the upper Waal River degrades around 1.5 cm/a (Chapter 1.1). Given those rough estimations and the assumption that the bed degradation proceeds in a similar and linear way, it would take around 20 to 300 a until the equilibrium is reached. However, this calculation is just included to give an idea of the order of magnitude of the time scale. Starting with the fact that slope adjustments are by no means linear processes (e.g. Figure 4.13; Sieben, 2012) and that the equilibrium slope range itself is of high uncertainty (Figure 4.1; Chapter 4.3), the estimation should be treated with great caution.

Again roughly estimated based on Figure 8 in RWS (2016b), the Waal River had slope of between 1.2×10^{-4} and 1.4×10^{-4} in 1850. This is approximately the equilibrium slope reached by the SN case when using the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) relation. The other transport relations, however, result in lower slope values. From the model runs, we can,

Figure 4.1: Resulting equilibrium slope and surface texture values for different cases predicted by different transport relations (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels; WC = Wilcock and Crowe; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen).

hence, conclude that even when on average doubling the incoming gravel load by SN, which is the measure that results in the greatest increase in slope, on the long-term the bed slope may still be smaller compared to its state of 1850. This is again given the assumption described in the previous chapters.

As illustrated, based on the assumptions, SN lead to an increase of the BC slope between 23 and 30 % which is equivalent to an increase of the bed level upstream of a 83 km reach of between 1.8 and 2 m. SN, as they are modeled here, thereby have the greatest impact on the slope in comparison with LD (slope increase of 10 %) and SC (slope increase of 5 %). These results are also illustrated by Figure 4.2 where the slope and sand content values presented in the previous figure (Figure 4.1) are compared to the BC values.

SN, furthermore, lead to a decrease of the equilibrium sand content (around 15 %), thus coarsening, whereas the other two measures have almost no impact on the equilibrium surface texture (Figures 4.1 and 4.2).

Results for extremer cases, with for instance for the SN case a tenfold increase of the gravel load instead of a doubling or a 20 % reduction of the water discharge instead of 5 % due to SC, can be found in Appendix C. One exemplary conclusion is the fact that when extracting 20 % of the water instead of 5 % in the SC case, and not changing any of the other assumptions, SC have approximately the same effect on the equilibrium slope as the SN, namely an increase of around 25 % compared to the BC. Another conclusion is that LD and SC may cause a significant increase in the equilibrium slope in case they lead to an extraction of one fourth of the water discharge from the main channel. However, this condition is unlikely to be fulfilled in the Waal River due to its navigation function and associated drought restrictions (Chapter 2.3). The examples show that the specific design of a measure affects its effectiveness. In the remainder of this study, we focus on the results of the cases defined in Table 3.4.

As a next step, we examine the predicted values resulting from using different transport relations. To simplify the examination, we have extended Figure 4.2 by the values of the different transport relations, in each case related to the BC value of the associated transport relation (Figure 4.3). We can see from the figure that the ratios of the slope

Figure 4.2: Slope and surface texture case values divided by the associated base case (BC) values using the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) relation (SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

and surface texture values are similar for the WC, the MPM, and the AM relation. The absolute slope and surface texture values predicted by the MPM and AM relation are lower compared to the ones predicted by the WC relation, meaning smaller equilibrium slopes and coarser equilibrium bed textures (Figure 4.1). The variation of the predicted values expresses the range of uncertainty given by the sediment transport relations.

The ratios of the slope and surface texture values when using the EH relation look somewhat different compared to the other three transport relations (WC, MPM, and AM) (Figure 4.3). We believe that the reason is that, as mentioned in Chapter 3.1, this relation is the only relation considered here that does not take hiding effects into account. As can be seen in Figure 4.3, the equilibrium surface texture in the SN case (when doubling the incoming gravel load) is for instance comparably coarse, meaning that the coarse fraction is relatively immobile compared to the other load relations. This is due to the fact that the EH load relation does not account for hiding effects, which makes the coarse sediment too immobile and, to compensate for this, the bed surface too coarse.

We can, hence, conclude that if comparing absolute values (Figure 4.1) the results for the equilibrium slope, unlike for the equilibrium sand content, predicted by the EH relation fall into the value range predicted by the other load relations (Figure 4.1). However, this range is relatively large. Yet, if comparing the relative change of equilibrium slope and surface texture resulting from different measures with each other, regardless the absolute values, the transport relations can be used interchangeably as long as hiding and exposure is considered (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3: Slope and surface texture case values divided by the associated base case (BC) values as a function of different transport relations (SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels; WC = Wilcock and Crowe; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Englund and Hansen).

4.2 Time Scale of the Response to the Measures

Having discussed the equilibrium states resulting from the considered cases, we now want to study the adjustments from one initial equilibrium state to the new equilibrium states resulting from the three measure cases. As mentioned before, we used the BC equilibrium as initial condition. For this purpose, we have run the numerical models. We have selected a reach of 300 km and limit the analysis to the upstream 100 km unaffected by backwater.

The Figure 4.4 shows the longitudinal profiles, the blue lines resulting from the BC, the colored lines resulting respectively from one of the measures cases. In accordance with the analytical results presented in the previous chapter, SN, as they are modeled here, lead to the largest increase in slope (Figure 4.1) or bed elevation (Figure 4.4) compared to the other measures.

In Figures 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7, the slope values resulting from the numerical models are plotted against the streamwise coordinate. The figures, furthermore, include the values derived from the analytical models (Figure 4.1), here the solid lines over the first 100 km. As can be seen, in this domain, the values from the analytical models match the initial and final slope values of the numerical models. Three conclusions can be drawn from this, also holding for the surface texture considerations (Figures 4.14, 4.15, and 4.16):

- The analytical results and the numerical results in the domain of the first 100 km match with each other regarding the equilibrium state. As the analytical model only holds in the normal flow zone, in the first 100 km we are, thus, indeed sufficiently far upstream from the backwater zone.
- Within the period of 10 000 a the equilibrium states are reached.

In the following, we focus on the adjustment of the river bed. Figures 4.2, 4.9 and 4.10 show the bed elevation over km 4 to 8. As can be seen, in the case of LD and SC only aggradation occurs as adjustment towards a new equilibrium. In the SN case, however, a degradational wave travels downstream preceding the aggradational wave (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.4: Initial and final bed elevation resulting from three different measures predicted by the numerical models (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure 4.5: Sediment nourishments (SN): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure 4.6: Longitudinal dams (LD): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure 4.7: Side channels (SC): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure 4.8: Sediment nourishments (SN) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

This matches the findings of Blom (2016) that have already been addressed in Chapter 2.1. If imposing a coarsening of the upstream sediment supply, SN can lead to downstream degradation preceding aggradation. This phenomenon and the negative consequences that might be connected to initial degradational waves should, hence, be taken into account when designing SN measures.

Chavarrías et al. (2018) have introduced the problem of ellipticity causing the model results to be unstable to short-wave perturbations. The models used in this research have been checked regarding this property and are found not to be elliptic.

To provide information on the time scale of the slope adjustments, we have reduced the length from 300 km to 100 km, as it is closer to the actual length of the Waal River. This is to account for the fact that the time scale depends on the length of the reach. Longer reaches require more time to adjust to an increased slope as more sediment has to be displaced (Figure 4.11). In fact, the time for the adjustment T increases quadratically with the length of the reach L ($T \sim L^2$) (De Vries, 1975), meaning that a the time scale for a three times larger reach is about nine times longer. When comparing the results of the 100 km reach (Figures 4.13, E.11 and E.12 in Appendix E) with the 300 km reach included in the Appendix D we can indeed find this order of magnitude relation.

Figure 4.12 illustrates how the half-time is defined in this work for different cases. We determine the maximum difference between the final slope or surface texture state and the initial one (Δz). The half-time ($T_{1/2}$) is defined as the time that the bed requires for half of the adjustment of Δz .

The half-time of the bed level adjustment varies between 200 a and 500 a depending on the location and the measure. This matches with the order of magnitude suggested by De Vries (1975). Again depending on the location and the measure, the aggradation rates at the half-time of the bed elevation adjustment is between 0.04 cm/a and 0.3 cm/a (calculated based on the tangents indicated in Figure 4.13 and in Figures E.11 and E.12 in Appendix E).

Regarding the surface texture adjustment, we provide plots similar to the ones presented for the bed elevation and the slope adjustment. Figure 4.14, 4.15 and 4.16 show that

Figure 4.9: Longitudinal dams (LD) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure 4.10: Side channels (SC) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure 4.11: Comparison of the slope adjustment depending on the reach length L (time scale $T \sim L^2$).

Figure 4.12: Schematic for the definition of half-time ($T_{1/2}$) for the bed elevation and surface texture adjustments.

Figure 4.13: Sediment nourishments (SN): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure 4.14: Sediment nourishments (SN): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

within the period of 10 000 a the equilibrium surface texture is reached. In the case of SN, we can see that the coarsening progress starts immediately after the implementation of the measure. Noteworthy are the fining waves in the first years in the case of LD and SC until the new equilibrium surface texture is reached. In other words, in those cases the aggradational waves, mentioned previously, are of finer material than the initial and final surface texture. We explain this feature with the fact that the temporal reduction of the sediment transport capacity due to the extraction of water in both cases has most effect on the sand transport as this fraction makes up most of the incoming load. The aggradation is, hence, mainly reached by the accumulation of sand due to water extraction. Water extraction, having an impact on the equilibrium slope, on the contrary has no effect on the equilibrium surface texture, as the texture depends on the mobility and availability of the grains. This corresponds to the results of the sensitivity analysis (e.g. Figure 4.20) and the constant relation between the water discharge and the equilibrium surface texture illustrated in Figure F.6 in Appendix F. It, furthermore, matches the findings of Blom et al. (2016). The argumentation for the fining waves, however, has not further been studied and, hence, should be object of a future research project.

Finally, the time scale of the adjustment of the surface texture is studied, here illustrated for each of the measures cases in the Figures 4.17, 4.18 and 4.19. The figures show the immediate coarsening in the SN case and the fining waves in the other two cases within about the first 200 a. In comparison with the adjustment of the bed elevation discussed before (half-time between 200 and 500 a), the surface texture adjustment is faster with an approximate half-time between 100 and 300 a.

Figure 4.15: Longitudinal dams (LD): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure 4.16: Side channels (SC): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure 4.17: Sediment nourishments (SN): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure 4.18: Longitudinal dams (LD): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure 4.19: Side channels (SC): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

Having discussed the results of the analytical and numerical models, we now want to study the results of the sensitivity analysis and hence answer RQ 4. In the sensitivity analysis, the same parameters are tested as the ones listed in Table 3.4, varying from the minimum to the maximum value of the range indicated in that same table. When varying one parameter from the minimum value to the maximum value, all other settings are kept constant.

The results are summarized in the figures presented in this chapter (Figures 4.20, 4.21, 4.22, 4.23). Each of the four figures presents one of the considered cases (BC, SN, LD, SC). The solid and dashed horizontal lines are equivalent to the lines in Figure 4.1. They present the equilibrium slope and surface texture resulting from different transport relations. The vertical lines show the slope and surface texture ranges resulting from the min-max ranges for each parameter, whereby the red arrows directed upwards display the results for the maximum values and the downwards directed green arrows the results of the minimum values. Arrows at the ends of one vertical line that are pointing in opposite directions, thus, indicate a positive relation between the parameter under consideration and the slope or the surface texture. Conversely, arrows pointing towards each other represent a negative relation. As mentioned before, the exact types of the relations, constant, linear or non-linear can be retrieved from the figures in the Appendix F.

The results from the sensitivity analysis are inherently linked to three influencing factors:

1. The first influencing factor is the way how the measures have been modeled (e.g. the decision to double the gravel supply in the case of SN).
2. Another factor is the range of the parameter value given in Table 3.4. If slope or surface texture depend on a certain parameter, a larger range leads to higher changes in the resulting slope or surface texture value compared to the original value.
3. The third factor is the actual physical response to a change in a certain parameter. According to the findings of Blom et al. (2016) and Blom et al. (2017), for instance, gravel transport dominates equilibrium slope and surface texture. The results of the sensitivity analysis may, hence, reflect this fact.

Figure 4.20: Slope and surface texture values resulting from the sensitivity analysis of the base case (BC) based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (values from each of the parameters varying from the minimum value (min) to the maximum value (max) while respectively the other parameters are kept constant; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen; B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

Figure 4.21: Slope and surface texture values resulting from the sensitivity analysis of the sediment nourishments (SN) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (values from each of the parameters varying from the minimum value (min) to the maximum value (max) while respectively the other parameters are kept constant; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen; B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

Figure 4.22: Slope and surface texture values resulting from the sensitivity analysis of the longitudinal dams (LD) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (values from each of the parameters varying from the minimum value (min) to the maximum value (max) while respectively the other parameters are kept constant; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen; B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

Figure 4.23: Slope and surface texture values resulting from the sensitivity analysis of the side channels (SC) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (values from each of the parameters varying from the minimum value (min) to the maximum value (max) while respectively the other parameters are kept constant; MPM = Meyer-Peter and Müller; AM = Ashida and Michiue; EH = Engelund and Hansen; B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

As can be seen from Figures 4.20, 4.21, 4.22 and 4.23, both the slope and the surface texture results are indeed particularly sensitive to the gravel size D_g and the gravel supply Q_g . Assuming a fourfold instead of a twofold gravel supply Q_g in the SN case (+ 100 %) leads to a surface texture consisting to around 40 % out of sand (Figure 4.21). This information is also included in the upper table of Appendix C. By implication, decreasing the original gravel supply value by 100 %, hence assuming that only sand load comes from upstream, logically leads to a pure sand river bed (sand content values of 1 in the figures). We believe that the influence of the first two factors named above is relatively low in this case and that the actual physical response (factor 3), also found by Blom et al. (2016) and Blom et al. (2017), is the main reason for the high sensitivity to the gravel size and supply. The reason for this is that even if the original gravel supply of the SN case is increased by 100 %, gravel still only makes up for about 30 % (originally 20 %) of the sediment supply.

Given the assumptions, the sensitivity to the channel width B is negligible for both the slope and the surface texture. The slope is, furthermore, rather insensitive to the sand load Q_s . In contrast, the slope results do change significantly with the friction coefficient c_f . For instance, computing the BC with the range of the friction coefficient (Chézy values between 44 and 55 $\text{m}^{1/2}/\text{s}$) leads to a relatively large resulting slope range between 1.2×10^{-4} and 0.7×10^{-4} .

From Figures 4.20, 4.21, 4.22 and 4.23, we can also see that the equilibrium surface texture is independent of the water discharge factor p_w . Furthermore, as already mentioned, it should be noted that the porosity p is not part of the analytical equations and hence changing the value has no impact on the model results. The sensitivity to parameters like the porosity p or the active layer thickness L_a (Table 3.2) in the numerical models could be worth another examination. Especially L_a is usually found to have a strong effect on the model outcomes (Mosselman, 2003).

We want to make a final remark regarding the result of the sensitivity analysis. It should be noted that the ranges of parameter values which have been applied are the same for all the considered cases. Therefore, when dividing the resulting value ranges from the measure cases by the BC ranges, the outcome is in most of the cases the same increase or decrease of the slope or surface texture BC values as displayed in Figure 4.2. This, however, only holds when the relation of parameter and the slope or the surface texture is of constant or linear nature. In any other case (parameters D_g , D_s , Q_g , Q_s), the ratio does differ from the values given in Figure 4.2. For the sake of completeness, the corresponding figures are implemented in Appendix G.

5 Discussion

There are many limitations resulting from the idealized analytical and numerical modeling approaches, which have already been addressed throughout the report. They raise questions that could further be investigated. In the following, we discuss some of the main limitations and how they might have affected the results of the models.

- The numerical models used in this work are one-dimensional. It may, however, be instructive to compare the results with both the results of multidimensional models and measurements from the field. Mosselman (2001), for instance, points out that in order to achieve a proper assessment of the morphological development of SC, a two-dimensional or three-dimensional approach is mandatory. For this reason, as a next step, we recommend applying a multidimensional model.
- As pointed out in Chapter 3.2, we have assumed that the shear stress does not further increase once the bankfull discharge is exceeded. Higher shear stresses, however, mean a decrease in the equilibrium channel slope. We recommend using models that do not require this assumption.
- In the numerical model approach, we have assumed the equilibrium state of the BC as initial condition. In reality, however, current morphological change influences the effectivity of the measures. Examples are the ongoing bed degradation, changes due to the SN in the Niederrhein, or changes due to measures in the scope of programs such as Ruimte voor de Rivier (RvR) to increase the capacity of the river to cope with high water levels (RWS, 2016a). The ongoing bed degradation, for instance, might change the distribution of water and sediment at the Pannerdensche Kop (RWS, 2016a), which would change the morphodynamics in the Waal River. We recommend further study into how current changes influence the effectivity of measures for mitigating the bed degradation.
- Another source of uncertainty refers to the schematization of the measures. In this research project, the values of four parameters (channel width; gravel load; sand load; water discharge) have been changed, compared to the base case, to model the measures. We have, furthermore, limited the study to the investigation of the main channel. It would, however, be interesting to see how different approaches, for instance, to regularly elevate the bed level in the SN case instead of increasing the sediment supply or nourishments at several locations, affect the results of the models. We have assumed that the LD and SC measures are implemented over the entire length of the idealized Waal River. What would, however, the equilibrium slope and surface texture look like if the measures cover only a certain part of the reach? How would the values change if, in the SN case, the increase in sediment supply would be spread over different locations along the reach? And regarding the limitation to the main channel, how do the secondary channels or side channels develop morphodynamically? How do those developments affect the effectivity of the LD or SC regarding the mitigation of the bed degradation in the main channel?

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- The last aspect addressed here refers to the assessment of effectivity. Here, we have assumed that the increase in bed slope achieved by the implementation of SN in an idealized Waal River can be defined as significant. However, the specific consequences that such an increase would have for the Waal River have not thoroughly been investigated. In order to improve the assessment of the effectivity of measures and, eventually, decision-making processes, we therefore want to raise another question: How do we define and measure project success? In other words, what increase in slope or change in surface texture makes a measure effective regarding the mitigation of bed degradation?

6 Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, we answer the five research questions that have been defined in Chapter 1.2.

1. How can we schematize the three measures in idealized analytical and numerical models?

We have modeled the Waal River in an idealized way using both an analytical and a numerical approach, and using values for the input parameters that have been decided upon on the basis of literature research and the consultation of experts. A base case (BC) has been used as the initial state for the consideration of different measures in the numerical models. In view of the goal to provide an order of magnitude comparison of morphodynamic changes in the main channel, we have limited the modification of the input values to, in total, four parameters to model the three measures. We have assumed a decreased water discharge and sediment supply values in the longitudinal dams (LD) and side channels (SC) case, an increased sediment supply value in the sediment nourishments (SN) case, and, furthermore, a reduced main channel width in the case of LD.

2. How do the three measures affect the equilibrium state regarding channel slope and the bed surface texture?

The range for the equilibrium slope resulting from the BC consideration matches the prediction made by RWS (2016b) (between 0.7×10^{-4} and 1.0×10^{-4}). This range is smaller than the measured value range for the Waal River from De Vries (1993), Sieben (2009), Sloff et al. (2014), and Blom (2016) (1.0×10^{-4} and 1.2×10^{-4}), which supports the observations of an ongoing bed degradation in the river.

The results of the models show that SN, as they have been modeled here, have the greatest effect on the equilibrium state. They lead to a significant increase in the bed slope as well as to coarsening of the surface texture. LD and SC also show an increase in slope, however, their effect is small. Their effect on the surface texture of the main channel is negligible.

The results, furthermore, indicate the high uncertainty given by the sediment transport relation assumed for the determination of the equilibrium slope and surface texture. If comparing absolute values the results for the equilibrium slope, unlike for the equilibrium sand content, predicted by the Engelund and Hansen (EH) relation fall into the value range predicted by the other load relations (Wilcock and Crowe; Ashida and Michiue; Meyer-Peter and Müller). If comparing the relative change of equilibrium slope and surface texture resulting from different measures with each other, regardless the absolute values, the transport relations can be used interchangeably as long as hiding and exposure is considered, which is not the case for the EH relation.

3. What is the time scale of the adjustment of the bed elevation and bed surface texture?

The results of the numerical models show a half-time for the bed level adjustment of several centuries (200 a and 500 a), which corresponds to the order of magnitude suggested by De Vries (1975) for base level change. Compared to the slope adjustment, the surface texture adjustment is somewhat faster but it is in the same order of magnitude (100 a and 300 a).

In addition to that, the results of the numerical models point to an initial degradational wave traveling downstream preceding the aggradational wave in the SN case, which matches the findings of Blom (2016). Furthermore, in the LD and SC case, the results indicate a fining of the bed surface, before nearly returning to the original value.

4. How sensitive are the results of the analytical models to the settings of various parameters?

The results of the analytical models are particularly sensitive to the parameters gravel size and gravel load. The fact that gravel transport seems to dominate the equilibrium slope and surface texture matches the findings of Blom et al. (2016) and Blom et al. (2017). The slope is also sensitive to the friction coefficient and the water discharge. Given the assumptions, the sensitivity of the slope to other parameters like the channel width are of minor significance. The sensitivity of the equilibrium surface texture to the channel width is negligible as well.

5. How effectively would the three measures serve the goal of mitigating the bed degradation?

Given the limitations of the research approach, the results of the models indicate that SN are most effective to increase the slope and, hence, to mitigate bed degradation in an idealized Waal River. As mentioned before, this measure, however, is associated with a preceding degradational wave, which, in the short term, can have negative consequences for river functions. This should be taken into account when planning SN.

Depending on the design of LD and SC, the results show that also these measures can significantly change the equilibrium slope and surface texture. We recommend to investigate a combination of different measures in a future project.

We want to conclude with the following remark. The models presented in this work are highly idealized and have many limitations. In the previous chapter, we have discussed some of the main limitations resulting from the modeling approaches. This work should, hence, be regarded as a basis on which further research can be conducted. In particular, we recommend to further investigate the shear stress assumption resulting from a rectangular cross section, how current changes influence the effectivity of measures, the schematization of the measures used in this research and assessment of effectivity, which have been addressed in the previous chapter. This may provide important insights and steer the direction of further research to improve measures for mitigating the bed degradation. Despite the long list of assumptions and simplifications, we believe that the order of magnitude comparison presented here provides indicative information.

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A Interviewed Experts

The experts listed below have been interviewed in the period between April 9th and April 24th, 2018. The interviews were based on four broad questions:

1. How does the ongoing bed degradation affect your field of work? How was/is your work related with the ongoing bed degradation? / *Hoe beïnvloedt de voortgaande bodemerosie uw werkveld? Hoe is uw werk verbonden met de voortgaande bodemerosie?*
2. What is your opinion on measures for mitigating the ongoing bed degradation such as SN, LD and SC? Do you see advantages/ disadvantages resulting from these? Do you have other promising measures/ ideas in mind for mitigating the bed degradation? / *Wat vindt u van maatregelen om de voortgaande bodemerosie tegen te gaan zoals sediment suppleties, langsdammen en nevengeulen? Ziet u bepaalde voor- en nadelen die met de maatregelen verbonden zijn? Heeft u andere ideeën om de bodemerosie tegen te gaan?*
3. What, from your perspective, is the main gap in knowledge with respect to measures for mitigating the bed degradation? *Waar, denkt u, is het grootste gebrek aan kennis ten aanzien van maatregelen tegen de bodemerosie?*
4. Do you have any further recommendations for my project/ for literature? / *Heeft u nog een advies voor mijn project of voor literatuur?*

Name	Institution
Dietmar Abel	Wasser- und Schifffahrtsamt (WSA) Duisburg-Rhein
Hermjan Barneveld	HKV Consultants
Marleen Buitendijk	BLN-Schuttevaer
Henk Eerden	Rijkswaterstaat Oost-Nederland
Habersack	Universität für Bodenkultur Wien
Erik Mosselman	Deltares; Delft University of Technology
Susanne Quartel	Rijkswaterstaat Oost-Nederland
Ralph Schielen	Rijkswaterstaat Water, Verkeer en Leefomgeving
Arjan Sieben	Rijkswaterstaat Water, Verkeer en Leefomgeving
Kees Sloff	Deltares; Delft University of Technology
Arjan Tuijnder	Arcadis
Stefan Volmer	Bundesanstalt für Gewässerkunde (BfG)

B Effects of Measures on the Equilibrium Slope

The figure in this Appendix is an extension of Figure 3.6 in Chapter 3.3 showing initial flow velocities and morphodynamic trends, in addition to the initial situations (top) and the new equilibrium situations (bottom) resulting from different measures.

C Cases Variations

This Appendix includes the results of the analytical models when different cases are considered, assuming the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) relation. The table on top refers to the sediment nourishments (SN) case, the table in the middle to the longitudinal dams (LD) case, and the table on the bottom to the side channels (SC) case. The bold numbers show the original settings (also listed in Table 3.4) and the resulting values used for the figures in Chapter 4.1. In Chapter 4.1, we have already given one exemplary conclusion is the fact that when extracting 20% of the water instead of 5% in the SC case, and not changing any of the other assumptions, SC have approximately the same effect on the equilibrium slope as SN, namely an increase of around 25% (change $i_{b0} = 1.25$) compared to the base case (BC).

BC	SN	Original: 1.00xQw; 2.00xQg; 1.00xQs; B=260 m											
Parameter change*		2xQg	4xQg	10xQg	2xQs	4xQs	10xQs	2xQg	4xQg	10xQg	2xQs	4xQs	10xQs
ib0	9.61E-05	1.18E-04	1.50E-04	2.22E-04	1.08E-04	1.34E-04	2.25E-04	1.31E-04	1.86E-04	2.25E-04	1.36	1.93	3.19E-04
change ib0	1.00	1.23	1.57	2.31	1.12	1.39	2.34	1.36	1.64	2.34	1.08	1.16	1.25
Fk0	0.59	0.51	0.41	0.28	0.74	0.87	0.96	0.64	0.69	0.96	0.64	0.69	0.74
change Fk0	1.00	0.85	0.69	0.48	1.24	1.46	1.61	1.08	1.16	1.61	1.08	1.16	1.25

BC	LD	Original: 0.85xQw; 1.00xQg; 0.95xQs; B=230 m										
Parameter change*		0.85xQw	0.95Qw	0.7xQw	0.95xQs	0.9xQs	0.8xQs	0.98xQg	0.95xQg	0.7xQw	0.8xQs	0.95xQg
ib0	9.61E-05	1.05E-04	9.35E-05	1.27E-04	1.05E-04	1.04E-04	1.02E-04	1.04E-04	1.03E-04	1.04E-04	1.07	1.27
change ib0	1.00	1.09	0.97	1.32	1.09	1.08	1.07	1.08	1.07	1.08	1.07	1.27
Fk0	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.58	0.56	0.59	0.60	0.59	0.59	0.57
change Fk0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.98	0.94	1.00	1.01	0.98	1.01	0.95

BC	SC	Original: 0.95xQw; 1.00xQg; 0.98xQs; B=260 m											
Parameter change*		0.95xQw	0.9xQw	0.85xQw	0.8xQw	0.98xQs	0.95xQs	0.9xQw	0.95xQs	0.8Qw	0.9Qs	0.8xQw	0.98xQg
ib0	9.61E-05	1.01E-04	1.06E-04	1.13E-04	1.20E-04	1.01E-04	1.00E-04	1.06E-04	1.06E-04	1.19E-04	1.23	1.18E-04	
change ib0	1.00	1.05	1.11	1.17	1.25	1.05	1.05	1.10	1.05	1.23	1.23	1.23	
Fk0	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.59	0.58	0.58	0.58	0.57	0.57	0.58	
change Fk0	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.97	

ib0 = Equil. slope predicted using the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) relation

Fk0 = Equil. sand content predicted using the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) relation

bold = Original setting of changed parameters

* All the other parameters are according to the original settings

D Time Scale of Bed Elevation Adjustment

In Chapter 3.3, we have presented the time scale for the bed elevation of a 100 km reach instead of a reach of 300 km. The reason for this is the relation between the length of the reach and the time for the adjustment. In this Appendix, however, we present the resulting time scales of the 300 km reach, which can be compared to the Figures 4.13, 4.13, and 4.13 in Chapter 4.1.

Figure D.1: Sediment nourishments (SN): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure D.2: Longitudinal dams (LD): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) - km-1 (top).

Figure D.3: Side channels (SC): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

E Numerical Results for a Reach of 100 km

Appendix E shows the remaining results of the numerical models for a reach of 100 km instead of 300 km (Chapter 4.1).

Figure E.1: Initial and final bed elevation resulting from three different measures predicted by the numerical models (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure E.2: Sediment nourishments (SN) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure E.3: Longitudinal dams (LD) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure E.4: Side channels (SC) (km-4 to km-8): Initial bed elevation (dashed line) and bed elevations of every year of the first 10 years (gray lines) (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a; BC = base case).

Figure E.5: Sediment nourishments (SN): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.6: Longitudinal dams (LD): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.7: Side channels (SC): Initial and final slope (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.8: Sediment nourishments (SN): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.9: Longitudinal dams (LD): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.10: Side channels (SC): Initial and final surface texture (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) (colored solid lines from the analytical models; BC = base case).

Figure E.11: Longitudinal dams (LD): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a) - km-1 (top).

Figure E.12: Side channels (SC): Time scale for the bed elevation adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 300 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure E.13: Sediment nourishments (SN): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure E.14: Longitudinal dams (LD): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

Figure E.15: Side channels (SC): Time scale for the surface texture adjustment (Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation; domain length = 100 km; simulation time = 10 000 a).

F Sensitivity Analysis Relations

In the following, the relations between the parameters of the sensitivity analysis (B , D_g , D_s , Q_g , Q_s , p_w , c_f , and p) and the slope or the surface texture are presented. Those relations have been the basis for the figures discussed in Chapter 4.3.

Figure F.1: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter channel width B based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.2: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter gravel size D_g based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.3: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter sand size D_s based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.4: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter gravel load Q_g based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.5: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter sand load Q_s based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.6: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter water discharge factor p_w based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.7: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter friction coefficient c_f based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

Figure F.8: Slope and surface texture as a function of the parameter porosity p based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (BC = base case; SN = sediment nourishments; LD = longitudinal dams; SC = side channels).

G Sensitivity Analysis Ratios

This Appendix shows the resulting cases values from the sensitivity analysis divided by the resulting BC values from the sensitivity analysis. Those figures can be compared to Figure 4.2 in Chapter 4.1.

Figure G.1: Sensitivity analysis ratios for the sediment nourishments (SN) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

Figure G.2: Sensitivity analysis ratios for the longitudinal dams (LD) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).

Figure G.3: Sensitivity analysis ratios for the side channels (SC) case based on the Wilcock and Crowe (WC) transport relation (B = channel width; D_g = gravel size; D_s = sand size; Q_g = gravel load; Q_s = sand load; p_w = water discharge factor; c_f = friction coefficient; p = porosity).